
**MILITARY PATRIOTISM IN YOUTH FAMILY AND EDUCATION IN
FORMATION PSYCHOLOGICAL COOPERATION OF INSTITUTIONS
FACTORS**

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Annotation.

in the formation of young people, children with the future of the country as an independent and free person, family, neighborhood and school cooperation, comprehensive improvement of the educational process is of great importance, the effective organization of further strengthening of mutual cooperation will be the basis for the maturation of young people as a harmonious generation.

Keywords.

Cooperation, Society, solid, harmonious, initiative, concept, temperament, truthfulness.

One of the spiritual values, which is of great importance as society develops, is the feeling of patriotism. Patriotism is a quality inherent in individuals who have a deep respect for the history of the motherland, the people and fate, able to show examples of self-sacrifice in the interests of the motherland. Respect for the motherland, the people, love, a sense of trust are formed on the basis of certain common interests, goals, take a deep place in the hearts of people, influence their activities. Patriotism is love for the motherland. Without love, the heart does not fit. The motherland is bitter, only the heart that lived with the Love Of The Motherland loves humanity. Patriotism is the liberation of the Fatherland, the preservation of

the peace of parents, El-yurt, jigargoshas, physical and spiritual readiness for protection, thorough rearmament with the sirasrors of military patriotism, This Will is the acquisition of a certain knowledge. Patriotism is the protection of one's own land from any enemy, the sacrifice of one's life if necessary on the path of freedom of the nation, people, homeland, peace of El yurt. Patriotism, on the other hand, is the feeling inherent in the wise and righteous children of all nations in the world. As you know, each period and generation creates a unique spiritual heritage in life. Whatever the spiritual heritage is, so are the periods and generations. The author of spiritual heritage is the people's masses. Thanks to independence, our people are reviving their history and heritage of life. Every period of our life is being revisited, the true meaning of the jadidism movement is being revealed. The ideas of Chulpan, Fitrat, Botu, Usman Nazareth, Abdullah Qadiri and others are being conveyed to our people. Indeed, our people have long been rich in the vital qualities of a person. Patriotic education is one of the necessary tasks facing independent Uzbekistan. Because it was impossible to think about it at the time of the former schouro formation, nor to do it in practice. Uzbekistan, creating its own future, should educate its patriots, its defenders, ensure the inviolability of its territories. It is necessary to use various means to educate the military in the spirit of patriotism. The history of our people in particular, the path it takes, the historical events in it are examples.

The main educational focus in the upbringing of the younger generation is the family and school. The upbringing of a child in a family is considered an extremely delicate and complex issue, which requires etiquette, knowledge, upbringing from the parents. The educational work is a complex, high-level task, which is carried out in cooperation with educational institutions of the family and the neighborhood. In order for a child to develop as an independent and free person, it is necessary to ensure family strength in the first place. We must not forget that the family is the backbone of society. It is this school and neighborhood that complement the education in the family. The work of educational institutions, family and neighborhood in cooperation is necessary for the upbringing of a child, especially for the upbringing of his harmonious personality. The first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Adopted at the initiative of Karimov-in the process of implementing the state program of the Year of a strong family, special attention is paid to the issue of further strengthening cooperation between family, neighborhood, educational institutions, raising healthy, mature and harmonious young people in all respects. Nowadays-cooperation of family, neighborhood,

educational institutions is considered an important role in improving the moral environment in families and raising children raised in them based on the requirements of the Times and in the spirit of national values. For a human child, the family is the main Godmother, a godmother and a godmother who turns out to be ready for life. We feel that the qualities of his character, the strength of a person physically and spiritually-he is brought up, and if we associate him with the family, then his contribution to living is much greater. Being considered a branch of family - society, Jamia also develops rapidly, as long as it is strong and harmonious in all respects.

The results of the study are the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism (next-concept) - developed on the basis of the basic principles and priorities of the state youth policy implemented in our country, in the current complex era of globalization, in a rapidly developing environment of information and communication technologies, current tasks related to the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism and ways to solve them, determine the role and importance of state and non-governmental organizations, The most important concepts related to the preservation of our motherland as an eyeball, the glorification of its fame to the world, the absorption of life and professional skills into the hearts and minds of young people on the basis of knowledge and education from the very first childhood, and thus the education of true patriotic citizens of Uzbekistan form the main meaning and meaning of the concept.

Conclusion: in conclusion, in the preparation of the military, we can put military education at the highest level in every possible way, up to the command of the knowledge institution, the composition of Professor teachers, the commander, veterans, carrying out large measures in cooperation with parents in the formation of a sense of love for the motherland, love for the chosen profession, peace and tranquility of the people.

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